

**A REVIEW OF SOME THERAPEUTIC VALUES OF AFRICAN GIANT SNAIL
(*Archachatina marginata*)**

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ABSTRACT

African Giant Snail (*Archachatina marginata*) and their secretions, particularly snail mucin, offer a range of therapeutic benefits which include skin health, wound healing and potentially cancer prevention. In folk medicine, the bluish liquid obtained when the meat has been removed from the shell is good for infant development. African Giant Snail meat also contains pharmacological properties of value in countering high blood pressure. This review highlighted some therapeutic values of snails using qualitative methods. African Giant Snail and its constituents (through proximate and mineral composition of its foot and shell) have been used as complete haematinic, anti-inflammatory agent and haemostatic agent to effect its numerous healing actions. There is however, the need for more studies to ascertain the potential risks in snail secretions.

Keywords: African Giant Snail, Therapeutic, Values, *Archachatina marginata*